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Prevalence and Attitude Towards Drug Abuse Among Commercial Motor Drivers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State

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Abstract

This study investigated the Prevalence and Attitude towards Drug Abuse among Commercial Motor Drivers in Port Harcourt Metropolis, Rivers State. The research design used was descriptive survey. The population for this study was 500 registered commercial motor drivers (CMDs). A sample size of 300 drivers was purposively taken for the study. A validated self-structured questionnaire was used to collect data for the study. Analysis of the data was done using a frequency table, percentage and analysis of variance for test statistics. Findings were that 185 (67.5%) of the CMDs accepted using drugs to aid driving in Port Harcourt metropolis while only 89 (32.5%) of them did not. There was a significant difference in the attitude of commercial motor drivers on drug abuse based on age ($F_{3, 270}=17.127, p<.05$), educational qualification ($F_{3, 270}=29.493, p<.05$) and on years of experience ($F_{3, 270}=16.925, p<.05$) respectively. This study is expected to create new research areas on drug abuse and its effects. It was, therefore, recommended that commercial motor drivers should be advised to minimize the rate at which they use drugs to aid driving. The CMDs should not take alcohol shortly before and while driving. Public health workers and Road Safety Corps officials should regularly embark on enlightenment campaign against misuse of drugs by CMDs.

Keywords: Attitude, commercial motor drivers, drug abuse, prevalence, Port Harcourt Metropolis.